

Prosailurus bitis
Nototriton degiustoi

Liobatrachus zhaoi
Wealdenbatrachus sp.
Wealdenbatrachus jucarensis
Hyogobatrachus wadai

Iberobatrachus angelae

Rhadinosteus parvus
Genibatrachus baoshanensis

Neusibatrachus wilferi

Cordicephalus gracilis
Cratopipa novaolindensis

Exonopoides reuningi

Palaebatrachus grandipes
Palaebatrachus tobieni

Hymenochirus boettgeri
Pipa carvalhoi
Pipa parva
Pipa pipa
Pipa aspera
Pipa arrabali

Shelania pasquali

Silurana calcaratus
Silurana tropicalis
Kenopus amietii
Kenopus muelleri
Kenopus civivi
Kenopus borealis
Kenopus laevis
Kenopus vestitus
Kenopus wittei
Kenopus boumbaensis
Kenopus aliofraseri
Spea hammondi
Spea bomifrons
Scaphiopus couchii
Scaphiopus holbrooki
Scaphiopus hurterii
Pelodytes caucasicus

Pelobates fuscus
Pelobates cultripes
Pelobates varaldii

Eopelobates bayleianus

Megophrys boettgeri
Megophrys carinense
Megophrys nasuta
Leptobrachella pelodytoidea
Leptobrachium hasseltii
Leptobrachium lili
Hadromophryne natalensis
Nasikabatrachus sahyadrensis
Sooglossus sechellensis
Seymourophryne gardineri
Syrnaptura masoni
Melanobatrachus indicus
Asterophrys turpicola
Microphyla berdmorei
Metaphrynella surdانا
Kaloula pulchra
Uperodon systoma
Uperodon montanus
Paradoxophyla palmata
Anodonthyla boulegarii
Plethodontohyla inguinalis
Rhinophrynus pygmaea
Cophyla pollicaris
Cophyla pollicaris
Ctenophryne aequatorialis
Chiasmocleis masoni
Chiasmocleis bassleri
Dermatorotus muelleri
Hypopachus variolosus
Gastrophryne carolinensis
Ptychocheilus bicolor
Hemistocleis bicolor
Hemistocleis guineensis
Breviceps adpersus
Balebreviceps millmani
Balebreviceps cocodactylus
Spelaeophryne methneri
Callulina kisuwamsitu
Callulina krefftii
Acanthixalus spinosus
Kassina witei
Kassina senegalensis
Cardioglossa leucomystax
Cardioglossa cyaneospila
Cardioglossa melanocephala
Arthroleptis bivittatus
Arthroleptis adolffriederici
Arthroleptis affinis
Leptopelis notatus
Leptopelis christyi
Astylosternus diadematus
Nectophrynax major
Leptodactylodon ovatus
Leptodactylodon axillaris
Psychrolutes maculatus
Hildebrandtia ornata
Phrynobatrachus krefftii
Conraua goliath
Conraua crassipes
Microixalus spinosus
Odontobatrachus natator
Petropedetes palmipes
Petropedetes vulpiae
Petropedetes sp.
Pyxicephalus angusticeps
Pyxicephalus adpersus
Anthrophryne rattrayi
Nothophryne broadleyi
Tomopterna tuberculosa
Tomopterna delalandi
Tomopterna marmorata
Arthroleptella lightfooti
Natalobatrachus bonebergi
Pyrrhina paludicola
Microbatrachella capensis
Cacosternum boettgeri
Cacosternum namaquense
Cacosternum capense
Astrobatrachus kurichiyana
Nankaneetes corrugatus
Nectibatrachus aliciae
Nectibatrachus major
Platymantis pollinensis
Cornufer papuensis
Cornufer vertebralis
Cornufer hedigeri
Cornufer guentheri
Indirana phrynoderma
Waxekera spinosus
Walkerana diplosticta
Occidozygia laevis
Limnonectes macrocephalus
Limnonectes blythii
Pseudis variegata
Hopllobatrachus tigrinus
Hopllobatrachus occipitalis
Hylarana erythraea
Amnirana albolineata
Amnirana galamensis
Rana temporaria
Pelophylax esculentus
Pelophylax perezi
Lithobates pipiens
Lithobates capito
Lithobates clamitans
Lithobates catesbeianus
Boophis boehmei
Mantidactylus majori
Mantidactylus majori
Buergeria japonica
Theloderma asperum
Nyxialus pictus
Nyxialus pictus
Nyxialus spinosus
Chironomantis rufescens
Polypedates macrotis
Zhangixalus nigropunctatus
Zhangixalus demytsi
Phyllaudis petersi
Phyllaudis surdus
Phyllaudis worcesteri
Raorchestes nerostegona
Raorchestes ocellularis
Raorchestes galamensis
Raorchestes flavivularis
Raorchestes manohari
Raorchestes resplendens
Raorchestes primarrumpfi

Cratia gracilis
Eurycephalella alciniae

Arariphrynus placidoi

Calyptocephalella gayi
Telmatobufo venustus
Mixophyes schweileri
Craugastor longirostris
Craugastor rugulosus
Barycholos pulcher
Strabomantis anomalus
Strabomantis bufoniformis
Oreobates discoidalis
Oreobates guianensis
Niceforonia nigrovittata
Niceforonia araiodactyla
Ischnocnema gualteri
Brachycephalus ephippium
Brachycephalus albolineatus
Brachycephalus curupira
Brachycephalus coloratus
Adelophryne gutturosa
Phyllaudis petersi
Diasporus diazi
Eleutherodactylus glaphycomps
Eleutherodactylus dimidiatus
Eleutherodactylus orientalis
Eleutherodactylus atkinsi
Eleutherodactylus inoptatus
Eleutherodactylus karischmidtii
Eleutherodactylus martincensis
Eleutherodactylus johnstonei
Cypitobatrachus boulegarii
Hemiphractus bubalus
Hemiphractus proboscideus
Stefania scalae
Gastrotheca cornuta
Gastrotheca longipes
Gastrotheca plumbea
Gastrotheca dysprositata
Gastrotheca peruana
Gastrotheca pseustes
Ceratotrypa aurata
Ceratotrypa cranwelli
Ceratotrypa ornata
Chacophrys pierotii
Leptodactylus laevis
Leptodactylus lianensis
Leptodactylus asper
Thoropa miliaris
Zachaeus parvulus
Cyclorhamphus asper
Cyclorhamphus tubus
Hylodes asper
Crossodactylus trachystomus
Crossodactylus gaudichaudii
Hylasina sylvatica
Heteroglossus patagonicus
Limnomedusa macroglossa
Alsodes nodosus
Eupsophus roseus
Eupsophus vertebralis
Rhomboderma darwini
Telmatobius thompsoni
Telmatobius macrostomus
Telmatobius cuteus
Telmatobius auratus
Telmatobius scrochii
Telmatobius schreiteri
Telmatobius bovei
Proceratophrys azevedoi
Macrogeniophrys alipioi
Odontophrynus lavillai
Odontophrynus cordobae
Odontophrynus americanus
Odontophrynus occidentalis
Odontophrynus achalensis
Odontophrynus barrioi
Cruziohyla calcarifer
Agalychnis moreletii
Phyllomedusa bicolor
Phyllomedusa burmeisteri
Phyllomedusa sauvaigi
Litoria nasuta
Ranoidea caerulea
Ranoidea festuensis
Ranoidea aurea
Ranoidea dahlii
Ranoidea longipes
Ranoidea australis
Boana doanisi
Boana pulchella
Boana faber
Scinax granulosus
Scinax fuscovarius
Scinax acuminatus
Dendropsophus nanus
Pseudis platensis
Pseudis minuta
Phyllodytes septentrionalis
Phyllodytes rodriguesi
Osteopilus septentrionalis
Corythomantis greeningi
Aparasphenodon brunoi
Argenteohyla siemersi
Nymphobates rugiceps
Acris crepitans
Acris gryllus
Pseudacris ornata
Pseudacris trilineata
Pseudacris trilineata
Smiilisca fodiens
Triprion spinosus
Triprion petasatus
Phyllodytes arborea
Phyllodytes graciosus
Dryophytes cinereus
Dryophytes andersonii
Dryophytes chrysoscelis
Dryophytes femoralis
Allophryne ruthveni
Hyalinobatrachium fleischmanni
Centrolene buckleyi
Centrolene medemi
Centrolene peristicta
Vitreorana ritae
Teratohyla ameliae
Espadachana callistomma
Pulchrana flavopunctata
Sachalania orejuela
Cochranella mache
Cochranella granulosa
Pseudopaludicola falcipes
Pleurodema masoni
Pleurodema bufoninum
Pleurodema cinereum
Pleurodema brachyops
Edalorhina perezi
Edalorhina peruviana
Physalaemus cuvieri
Physalaemus biligonigerus
Physalaemus santafacini
Physalaemus fernandezae
Adenomera andreae
Leptodactylus chaquensis
Leptodactylus latrans
Leptodactylus laiceps
Leptodactylus gracilis
Leptodactylus latinasus
Leptodactylus mystaceus
Allobates inasperatus
Allobates kinabaluensis
Allobates femoralis
Ameerega trivittata
Colostethus poecilonotus
Hyloxalus bocagei
Phyllodytes bicolor
Oophaga pumilio
Dendrobates auratus
Dendrobates leucomelas
Melanophryniscus rubriventris
Melanophryniscus stelnzeri
Melanophryniscus estebani
Frostius pernambucensis
Atelopus oxyrhynchus
Atelopus zeteki
Atelopus igneus
Osornophryne guacamayo
Truebella tothastes
Truebella skoptes
Nannophryne variegata
Peltophryne guentheri
Peltophryne lighti
Rhaebo blombergi
Rhinella spinulosa
Rhinella ceratophrys
Rhinella masoni
Rhinella dorbignyi
Rhinella crucifer
Rhinella arenarum
Rhinella rupestris
Rhinella marina
Rhinella diptycha
Incilius alvarius
Incilius mazatlanensis
Incilius caferiensis
Incilius vauclerensis
Anaxyrus cognatus
Anaxyrus quercicus
Anaxyrus terrestris
Anaxyrus fowleri
Anaxyrus americanus
Anaxyrus woodhousii
Mertensophryne micranotis
Capensibufu sp.
Incilius capensis
Sclerophrys superciliosa
Sclerophrys regularis
Volterstorffia mirei
Nectophrynus affra
Bufo bufo
Rentapia hosii
Phrynosoma asper
Epidaleia calamita
Epidaleia viridis
Schismaderma carens
Nectophrynoides tornieri
Altiphrynoides malcolmi
Dutaphrynus melanoctictus
Peltophryne melanota
Didymophrynus marmoratus
Didymophrynus marmoratus
Ansonia penangensis
Ansonia mcgregori